

POLITICAL SCIENCES

RUSSIA'S ON GOING HYBRID WAR IN GEORGIA'S AND ITS INFLUENCE ON PROTECTED CONFLICT

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Abstract

The article will analyze a new generation war, Hybrid warfare, what is the powerful weapon of the Russian Federation. It Examines Russia's Hybrid war tools, techniques and their impact on protracted conflict in Georgia.

Keywords: Hybrid war, protracted conflicts, Russia's aggression.

Introduction:

In the wake of globalization and the development of information technology, a new type of war "Hybrid war" became the utmost important technique, used by the Russian Federation against Georgia in every possible direction.

In recent decades, the universe has been under threat – the widespread concept of hybrid war, which is a critical and ongoing challenge around the world, as it is a fight where borders and time do not matter and can be conducted openly and may pose a more devastating threat to countries in the future, than military confrontation between countries.

Furthermore, this war causes physical and material damage and controls people's psychology, emotions, and thoughts, so they may not even be aware of it. Consequently, the damage caused by the war and its subsequent compensation will be tricky for the world to overcome. Unfortunately, the new war strategy had a significant impact and still posed a great threat to Georgia's national security and the resolution of the protracted conflict. The damage and the results caused by this non-military war will be more prolonged and deep. Russia is using hybrid war elements, which are, as never, critically damageable to global security. Moscow's aggressive policy's main elements are exactly Hybrid war elements. It derives from the Conflict in Georgia, then broader in Crimea. Through the Hybrid War, the Russian Federation managed the bloodless annexation of Crimea, and now we have in the face of ongoing Russian aggression against the independence of Ukraine.

The Russian Federation uses all internal and external Hybrid War tools to destabilize these regions' situations and put political pressure on the governments. Therefore, non-military elements, with military elements, are weighty in Russian military thought. By using hybrid war, the basic, the Russian Federation can leverage and manipulate post-soviet space, especially in conflict and occupied zones.

To feed its empire, the Russian Federation, which constantly plays with the world by its own rules and never shies away from satisfying its imperial desires by military means, has crossed many red lines in front of the international community. It conquered the territories of neighboring countries using hybrid warfare, the

technologies he refined over time. 2008 Russo-Georgian War and the 2014 War in Ukraine are vivid examples of those above. Russia had created all the grounds for winning the war just before the start of the military intervention. Before the war, the Kremlin used its new war technologies to do major essential work before hostilities started.

The Russian military defines a "hybrid war" as a strategic-level effort to shape a target state's governance and geostrategic orientation in which all actions, up to and including the use of conventional military forces in regional conflicts, are subordinate to an information campaign.

It is worth mentioning, that Russian officials started calling for a comprehensive security doctrine around decades ago. In the political and strategic documents from 2010, the Kremlin deals more with the characteristics of modern conflicts, than directly with the armed forces. Its approach emphasizes the possibility of integrating military and non-military capabilities to enable Russia to maintain its role as a world center and remain an agent of influence in global space. Military doctrines of 2010 and 2014 also referred to the integrated use of military and non-military resources and means. By using the hybrid war techniques, protracted conflict in Georgia is becoming more complex, prolonged and intractable.

The importance of using elements of hybrid warfare in Russian military circles is being actively discussed. For example, in his 2013 report "The Methods of Conducting a New Generation War," the Chief of the General Staff of Russia, Valery Gerasimov, analyzed the events of the "Arab spring." He concluded that military force would be used secretly in a "new generation war" without an official statement. It emphasizes the importance of using information and economic and political forces. He also says it would be perfect if Russia started cooperating closely with the protest segment in the opposing country. Russia uses exactly mentioned methods in Georgia. The main goal of which is to spread an anti-Western narrative in society and finance non-governmental organizations or opposition political parties. He is trying to influence the foreign policy course of Georgia by using disinformation and propaganda methods.

On the other hand, it uses economic forces as one of the crucial hybrid war elements in the occupied regions of Georgia. According to the 2023 report of the State Security Service of Georgia, in 2023, the budget of the occupied region Abkhazia, Georgia was about 159 million dollars, of which about 41% (about 65 million dollars) was the Russian tranche. As for the occupied Tskhinvali region, the so-called budget was about 107 million dollars, of which about 78% (about 83.2 million dollars) was financed by the Russian Federation.²

Gerasimov's article is striking proof that Russia has developed a new combat strategy that significantly differs from the classical rules of war and has acquired a completely new hybrid character. Russia uses the information space as an essential tool in the theory of hybrid warfare. Russian TV channels **"Russia Today"** and **"Sputnik"** are powerful tools to spread information throughout the world that is beneficial to it and harmful to the West.

According to Valery Gerasimov, information and psychology play a significant role in modern conflicts. The author notes, that the significance of outdated military means is gradually diminishing, and states have to comprehend the role of non-military methods in achieving their goals, which are aimed at shaking the foundations of the state so that military means do not become necessary to defeat the enemy. Gerasimov thinks that the line of war can pass in all areas simultaneously in such wars. In concordance with his basic idea, the main target in modern warfare is the mind. Therefore, the dominant place in modern military operations is devoted to information and psychological wars. The Kremlin uses the mentioned the most often in the occupied territories of Georgia. Such actions create more obstacles in the way of solving or transformation of the conflict.

The author presented the second report in March 2019. According to Gerasimov, nowadays, to win the war, it is still necessary to use both military and non-military methods to ensure the success of the armed forces. It was especially noted that Russia developed its counter-strategy against any forms and strategies, which implies the so-called "active defense" and unites various active measures to ensure the state's security. It is noteworthy that Gerasimov directly refers to modern information technologies as weapons and views them as a means to achieve military and political objectives. He states that the information field, which has no clear national borders, is a tool that can have a hidden impact not only on critically important information infrastructure but also on the population of a country and, consequently, on the security of the country (Gerasimov, 2019).

After the military intervention in Georgia in 2008, Russia used only hybrid war methods to maintain and strengthen its influence over the territory of Georgia.

Which until now is sufficient to achieve his goal, of making the conflict in Georgia even more protracted. As I mentioned above, the more continuous the conflict, the more difficult it is to resolve it using traditional methods. The hybrid warfare idea is two-fold: to jeopardize the Euro-Atlantic integration process of Georgia, harm strategic cooperation with the Western world, and drift Georgia into the Kremlin's orbit.

Kremlin sees Tbilisi's pro-Western foreign policy agenda and aspirations to join the European and Euro-Atlantic space as a significant security threat. Moreover, the Kremlin understands that consolidating a Western-style democratic system with transparent and robust institutions in Georgia would represent a direct and visible contrast to the Russian authoritarian system, incentivizing other states to follow the Georgian example. Should also be mentioned Georgia's growing relations with NATO allies, caused significant dissatisfaction in the Kremlin. If Georgia becomes a member of the mentioned alliance, its territorial integrity and sovereignty will depend on its members, Herewith, after Georgia's integration into the EU, there is a huge chance, that Georgia's occupied territories may rethink their connections with Russia, who can offer them less, then Georgia, as one of the EU member countries. Considering the above-mentioned Russia uses a strong Hybrid war against Georgia in this direction. , create each possible obstacle in the way of Georgia's Western aspiration. The vivid proof of all this is its current efforts, to use the ongoing political situation in Georgia, regarding the low of foreign influence for its own best interests.

Russia perfectly used this momentum, and its official statements exaggerated current demonstrations. For more visibility, the Georgian Parliament's decision to pass a law on foreign influence has triggered widespread protests in the capital. Critics warn that it mirrors a foreign agents law already passed in Russia. Russia would not miss that chance definitely, its officials made just "simple" statements, that they are standing on the side of parliamentarians, and support the adoption of the mentioned law. It is doubtless, that Russia's official discourse has used information warfare as a "peacetime weapon"³ for destabilizing a target society, poured fuel on the fire, and increased uproar among the people. It is worth noting that the de-facto rulers of the occupied territories of Georgia and the "opposition" persons also made statements. For example, Akhra Bjanina, head of the Akhyatsa public movement, said that this law is Russian, which is why the Georgian government can take back Abkhazia from Russia as a "compromise".⁴ This cooperation is called mutual beneficial cooperation. „To me, the Georgian "foreign agents" bill is a kind of maturity test. When you have to choose one thing: either nostalgic past or life-affirming future“.

After the mentioned statements made in Russia, Even those people who had not read the law at all,

² <https://bm.ge/news/rogoria-okupirebuli-afkhazetisa-datskhinvalis-finansuri-damokidebuleba-rusetze-sus-is-angarishi>

³ <https://oc-media.org/abkhazian-opposition-figures-express-support-for-georgias-HYPERLINK> "https://oc-media.org/abkhazian-opposition-figures-express-support-

for-georgias-foreign-agent-law-protesters/" HYPERLINK <https://oc-media.org/abkhazian-opposition-figures-express-support-for-georgias-foreign-agent-law-protesters/>
⁴ (<https://jam-news.net/abkhazia-georgia-and-foreign-agents-bill/>

started chanting, that the bill initiated by the Parliament of Georgia was Russian because it was supported by Moscow. Because of protracted conflict, Georgians feel deep hostility toward the Kremlin and any statement or action is perceived by the masses as much more painful and aggressive. It is one of the important characteristics of a protracted conflict. The goal of such a kind of disinformation is to convince the audience with not only one message but also many directions. To change their overall mind. After all, of this, we have the face the statements by the Western governments, Matthew Miller, Spokesperson of the US Department of State mentioned, that the Kremlin supports the text proposal.⁵

Based on above example, vivid conclusion is that the main beneficial part of created processes in the capital of Georgia is the Russia Federation. Russia perfectly used the current events to its advantage and created a turbulent environment between Georgia and its strategic partners.

Another method to make Georgia far from the Western universe and Nato is the method of Borderization. Strikes the fear into that part of the society, if Georgia does not change its foreign policy vector and realizes the processes of integration in the Euro-Atlantic space, Russia will completely annex the occupied territories of Georgia. At the same time, tries to show that the West, which is “so kind to Georgia, does nothing in favor of Georgia to stop the steps towards this illegal annexation.

The impact of a hybrid war on a protracted conflict:

According to the scientist Peter Coleman,⁶ the longer protracted conflicts last, the fewer opportunities are for its resolution with traditional methods. Coleman considers protracted conflicts in the context of a dynamic model and argues that internal factors are becoming more and more resistant to external interference. Conflicts go through escalation and de-escalation phases, change forms, spread in new groups, and, possibly, will be passed down from generation to generation, in which, of course, **the media plays an important role.** When a conflict drags for a long time, the parties to the Conflict make an effort to keep the existence of the Conflict and its intense sensations from drowning in society and from being forgotten. That is why the best tool for that is the media and the social space, which the Kremlin fruitfully uses to undermine Georgia. Digital and social media are breeding grounds for disinformation, and Russia brings that into its strategic calculus. Disinformation peddled by Russia is sometimes very effective.

The Russian media in the occupied regions of Georgia (Abkhazia and Tskhinvali) play a significant role in recalling and interpreting wartime facts. Provid-

ing information to the population through such formations continuously serves the only purpose of the Kremlin - to further aggravate the syndrome of a broken bridge between Georgia and the occupied territories by constantly raising a sensitive issue. It also tries to pass on from generation to generation the enemy image of Georgia as a terrible legacy, which, of course, makes it even more challenging to resolve a protracted conflict in any situation, not just during a conflict.

According to Edward Azar's theory, emotional aspects are activated during a protracted conflict, which becomes even more vital as the Conflict continues. At this time, it is not easy to make a rational decision. The Russian propaganda machine is actively working to strengthen these emotions. According to Edward Azar's⁷ theory, another characteristic feature of protracted Conflict is that it lasts longer and is more complicated due to external interference; this or that side of the Conflict always considers the third party as an enemy. That is why the second element of Russia's information war is to present the West as an enemy both occupied regions of Georgia. Inhabitants believe, that West support Georgia and want to resolve the Conflict in favor of the Georgian side.

Putin's Moscow actively uses almost every element of the hybrid war – informational, economic, and political. Moscow controls all media and prints media on the territory of occupied Abkhazia. The population has almost no access to other international channels. The local media sector is dominated by the government, which operates the Abkhaz State Television and Radio Company (AGTRK), a newspaper, and a news agency. Russian TV and Abkhazian state TV are the main sources of news. State-run one – Apsua TV, which broadcasts up to 6 hours a day, with 15-minute news in Abkhaz and Russian, and is the only local channel available all over the territory. Major Russian stations are relayed in the territory. The only private TV, Abaza TV, is licensed to cover the entire region. There is little or no access to Georgian TV, other than by satellite.⁸ The second problem, which even complicates the issue, is the population's education level and the language barrier. Most of them know only Russian as a foreign language. Therefore, they will not be able to read anything except Russian information broadcast or published in other languages. Herewith, kremlin actively use social media as one of the strong hybrid war component. In 2021, CNN Business reported Russia and Iran as the top two sources of coordinated fake activity on Facebook. As for the occupied Tskhinvali region, the situation is even worse here. The language spoken by the vast majority of the population is Ossetia, reported only by Russian media outlets. The state news agency <https://cominf.org/> is top-rated and publishes the information that Kremlin agents want.

⁵ <https://1tv.ge/lang/en/news/matthew-miller-fara-is-for-people-who-act-on-behalf-of-foreign-governments-not-for-people-who-do-legitimate-non-governmental-organization-work/>

⁶ Characteristics of Protracted, Intractable Conflict: Toward the Development of a Metaframework Peter T. Coleman PEACE AND CONFLICT: JOURNAL OF PEACE PSYCHOLOGY, 9(1), 1–37

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⁷ EDWARD AZAR'S PROTRACTED SOCIAL CONFLICT THEORY AND DRIVERS OF SELF-DETERMINATION: THE CASE OF NIGERIA. Centre for International Peace and Stability – NUST University Islamabad. <http://studies.strategiczne.amu.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/ps-2021-17.pdf>

⁸ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-18175030>

According to the Freedom House 2020 research, local media, including the television channel and newspapers - Yuzhnaya Osetiya and Respublika, and the online portals are almost entirely controlled by the authorities. As a result, self-censorship is pervasive, and defamation charges are often employed against critical media. Nevertheless, the local version of the Russian news portal Sputnik, accessible in both Russian and Ossetia, is increasingly popular.⁹ Consequently, in such a situation, Russia does not even make much effort to create an information vacuum in the occupied Abkhazia and Tskhinvali regions for the local population and to keep their jingoistic sentiments constantly awake.

Russia's information war and propaganda in the occupied territories of Georgia mainly takes place in two directions: the first is to **constantly portray Georgia as an enemy**, the new generation to remember forever **"how bad the Georgians were"** and how they tried to seize their homeland, which led to the ruthless **extermination of the Abkhazians**. **The second** is to show how bad the West is, which is constantly biased, supports Georgia, and acts subjectively. Special attention is paid to the constant recollections of the past in the Russian interpretation to preserve and deepen the roots of hatred towards Georgia among the population.

For example, March 15-16, 1993, in occupied Abkhazia, is celebrated as the day of the liberation of Sukhumi from Georgia. Consequently, various events are constantly held in honor of the Abkhazian heroes who were "killed by Georgian troops," as well as the so-called historical and patriotic actions. "along the roads of heroes, the way to glory". "March 15-16 is a day of mourning in the country's history. Twenty-eight years ago, during an offensive operation to liberate Sukhumi from the invaders, Abkhazia lost 250 brave defenders of the homeland. A pain will always be with us. The young boys started attacking though they realized that they would die. Everything was done for our future, our homeland's future. They had the purest thoughts; they thought of a free Abkhazia where everyone would live peacefully".¹⁰ Looking through the information covered in 2024 concerning this day, we can see how propaganda machines try to enhance the enemy image of Georgia by spreading disinformation, which in the event of a protracted conflict, makes it much more challenging to resolve in any way. The primary purpose *is to awaken the hostile attitude towards Georgia again and call on the next generation never to forget how Georgians killed young heroes fighting for the homeland*. Statements of the so-called president of the occupied region of Abkhazia, Georgia also worse to mention Aslan Bzhania - "Dear compatriots! Today we celebrate one of the most tragic and at the same time heroic dates in the history of the Abkhazian Patriotic War. 28 years ago, on March 15, 1993, in battles, over 200 soldiers of the Abkhazian army died, hundreds of people were wounded, and over

20 were lost. We honor the memory of our heroes who sacrificed themselves for the freedom of Abkhazia. ***Our main task is to protect the independence of Abkhazia and make it a successful country because thousands of sons and daughters died for its freedom***". ***I dreamed of seeing it. Eternal glory to the heroes!***"¹¹ The same narrative is spread in the occupied region of Tskhinvali, Georgia.¹² ***We have not forgotten anything: in South Ossetia are commemorating the Tsinagar tragedy***". The article also states that these individuals fought for the independence of Ossetia and against the Georgians, **"who started our genocide in 1920 and ended it in 2008**. They were killing old people, mothers, and children. They wanted Ossetia without Ossetia's."¹³

Conclusion

As a result, in both stages situation is concerning, Central government of Georgia with its western strategic partners should intensify and unify all integrity efforts to counter hybrid campaign. Otherwise, as time passes, the chance of protracted conflict resolution will decrease.

One set of explanations is that the Russia Federation uses economic, military and information hybrid warfare elements to maintain its control over the occupied regions of Abkhazia and Tskhinvali, Georgia. Without any military intervention, it manages to prolong conflict. Meanwhile, protracted conflicts are not resolvable with ordinary methods. Shortly, as protracted it is, the harder is to resolve with simple theory in the foreseeable future. Kremlin perceives well, that during protracted conflict emotional experience of humiliation contribute to the enduring nature of intractable conflicts. Seizing this, the main objective is to make deeper people's physical, psychological and emotional traumas.

On another stage, while Georgia's Euro-Atlantic aspiration is alarming for Russia, as a set of hybrid warfare activities it creates instability in Georgia, to distance it from the Western world. Russia uses all the information sources at its disposal to enhance and intensify people's aggression towards to the Government. Georgia without western allies will be less attractive for the occupied Abkhazia and Tskhinvali regions. What is a guarantee of keeping the occupied territories of Georgia permanently under the Kremlin's control.

References

1. В Грузии у здания парламента собрались противники закона об иноагентах. Я. Тимофеев 15.04.2024 12:48 <https://rg.ru/2024/04/15/v-gruzii-u-zdaniia-parlamenta-sobralis-protivniki-zakona-ob-inoagentah.html>
2. C.R. Mitchel "Conflict, Social Change and Conflict Resolution. An Enquiry"
3. Protracted Social Conflict; Theory and Practice in the Middle East Edward E. Azar, Paul Jureidini and Ronald McLaurin

⁹ <https://freedomhouse.org/country/south-ossetia/freedom-world/2021>

¹⁰ <https://www.apsnypress.info/ru/item/2666-beslan-eshbamolodye-rebyata-shli-na-smert-radi-budushchego-nashej-rodiny>

¹¹ <https://www.apsnypress.info/ru/item/2661-prezident-aslan-bzhaniya-obratilsya-k-narodu-abkhazii-v-svyazi-s-28-oj-godovshchinox-martovskogo-nastupleniya>

¹² <http://cominf.org/en/node/1166535356>; <https://www.kavkaz-uzel.eu/articles/353097/>

¹³ <http://cominf.org/en/node/1166529595>

4. Journal of Palestine Studies Vol. 8, No. 1 (Autumn, 1978), pp. 41-60 (20 pages) Published By: University of California Press)
5. P. Collaman Robin. R“Protracted conflicts as dynamical systems” P.62-65lr_29.08.16.pdf protracted conflict and humanitarian action ICRC
6. https://www.icrc.org/sites/default/files/document/file_list/protracted_conflict_and_humanitarian_action_icrc_report_https://www.researchgate.net/publication/236007848_Protracted_Conflicts_as_Dynamical_Systems
7. Abkhazian opposition figures express support for Georgia’s foreign agent law protesters. Oc Media. 09.05.2024 <https://oc-media.org/abkhazian-opposition-figures-express-support-for-georgias-foreign-agent-law-protesters/>.
8. What will Georgians choose: their past embodied by Abkhazia or a European future? I. Khashig. 16.05.2024 <https://jam-news.net/abkhazia-georgia-and-foreign-agents-bill/>
9. Matthew Miller: FARA is for people who act on behalf of foreign gov’ts not for people who do legitimate NGO work 07.05.2024
10. <https://1tv.ge/lang/en/news/matthew-miller-fara-is-for-people-who-act-on-behalf-of-foreign-governments-not-for-people-who-do-legitimate-non-governmental-organization-work/>
11. Russia’s hybrid war against the West. A. Bilal. 26.04.2024
12. <https://www.nato.int/docu/review/articles/2024/04/26/russias-hybrid-war-against-the-west/>
13. RUSSIAN HYBRID WARFARE. MILITARY LEARNING AND THE FUTURE OF WAR SERIES09.2020
14. <https://www.understandingwar.org/report/russian-hybrid-warfare>
15. Сложно понять». Как Запад и Россия отреагировали на грузинский закон об иноагентах 16.05.2024
16. <https://rtvi.com/news/slozhno-ponyat-kak-zapad-i-rossiya-otreagirovali-na-gruzinskij-zakon-ob-inoagentah/>
17. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-18175030>
18. <https://freedomhouse.org/country/abkhazia/freedom-world/2023>
19. <https://www.apsnypress.info/ru/item/2660-segodnya-v-abkhazii-otmechayut-28-yu-godovshchinu-martovskoj-nastupatelnoj-operatsii>